

**Sovereignty over Life and Death: A Necropolitical
Reading of Bhavani Bhattacharya's *So Many
Hungers!***

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Abstract: *The Bengal Famine of 1943 stands as one of the darkest chapters in colonial India's history, marked by widespread hunger, suffering and death. It is estimated that approximately three million individuals perished during the Famine. Bhabani Bhattacharya's novel, So Many Hungers! (1947), offers a literary exploration of this catastrophic event and stands as a grim example of state power's role in shaping life and death. Drawing from Foucault's concept of biopolitics and Mbembe's notion of necropolitics, this article examines how British colonial governance directly contributed to mass starvation and deaths in Bengal. Biopolitics, to Foucault, refers to the state of administration in which modern colonial power utilises its biopower to regulate and control specific populations and individuals. Taking a cue from him, Achille Mbembe introduced Necropolitics, which refers to the politics of death, where state power determines who lives and who dies, making life unlivable for certain communities and individuals. Through the requisitioning of food supplies, prioritisation of military needs,*

and inadequate response to famine conditions, the colonial administration exercised sovereignty over the lives and deaths of millions of Bengalis. This article explores these themes by examining how colonial governance influenced the experiences of the Bengali people during this crisis. Through a close analysis of Bhattacharya's narrative and historical context, this endeavour aims to uncover the dynamics of power, survival and resilience in the face of adversity.

Keywords: Necropolitics, Biopolitics, Bengal Famine 1943, Death, State of exception, Sovereignty

Introduction

1943 was a turbulent year for India under British colonial rule during World War II. Trade disruptions, the diversion of resources, and military demands deepened shortages of food and essential goods. Indian soldiers fought abroad, while at home, the Quit India Movement of 1942 had sparked mass protests, met with brutal repression, but it yet it strengthened the determination for independence. Meanwhile, Japanese advances through Burma threatened India. Yet the most devastating crisis, the Bengal Famine of 1943, remained largely undocumented. Caused by war conditions, poor policies, hoarding, and natural factors, it claimed millions of lives, devastating Bengal's poor and leaving one of South Asia's worst tragedies. It was devastating in terms of its scale, causing three million deaths, and occurred during the midst of World War II, when India was under the British Raj (Mallik 3209). The Great Bengal Famine of 1943 is a dark chapter in the history of India, particularly Bengal, where millions suffered from hunger and deprivation during a time of global conflict. This famine unfolded against the backdrop of World War II, a period already marked by hardships and uncertainties. Bengal, an agricultural region known as the "rice bowl of India," faced additional challenges due to natural disasters such as storms and floods, which destroyed crops and worsened food shortages. The

British colonial rulers, who governed India at the time, prioritised their wartime needs over the well-being of the Indian population. Instead of providing relief and assistance to the starving masses, they imposed policies that further exacerbated the crisis. Senjuti Mallik rightly points out, “It also points out how the British authorities exacerbated the famine due to their incompetence and implementation of various erroneous governmental policies” (3206). Essential food supplies were diverted to support the war effort, leaving the local population to fend for themselves. As a result, millions of people, including women, children, and the elderly, faced starvation and sickness.

The consequences of the famine were devastating on multiple levels. Families were torn apart as individuals struggled to survive, and communities grappled with the loss of loved ones and the breakdown of social structures. The suffering and indignity experienced by the people of Bengal caused resentment and anger towards the British colonial rulers. Many saw the British administration's indifference to their plight as a stark betrayal of trust and a clear indication of their disregard for Indian lives. The Bengal Famine of 1943 was an anthropogenic disaster that devastated Bengal, modern-day Bangladesh, and parts of eastern India. It catalysed political mobilisation, strengthening the independence movement led by Gandhi, Nehru, and Bose. The famine became a stark symbol of colonial exploitation, deepening the demand for freedom from British rule. Millions perished, and its effects lingered as families struggled to rebuild shattered lives. The trauma left a lasting imprint on Bengal's collective memory, underscoring the need for effective governance and humanitarian aid. Yet the resilience and solidarity of the people in the face of immense suffering testified to human endurance.

Though different critics often criticize his novel for its narrative structure, storytelling, and fragmented style, Sourit Bhattacharya put it right by saying, “In order to capture this dialectic of fragmentation of the total system and the perception of totality, it becomes necessary for a socially committed writer to

follow a style of writing that is different from a conventionally written novel”(51) However, we see how the famine affected real lives, not just as a lack of food, but as a profound emotional and spiritual crisis. The author, through the use of stories about characters, reveals the multifaceted nature of the famine and its varied impacts on people. It wasn't just about not having enough to eat; it was also about feeling lost, alone, and disconnected from everything. Bhattacharya helps us understand that the famine wasn't just an accident; it happened because of unfairness and neglect by those in power. He shows us how colonialism played a big part in making things worse for people. Communities were torn apart, and people struggled to find their place in a changed world. But even in the darkest times, the book reminds us of the resilience of the human spirit. It teaches us to look back at history, to understand where we come from, and to learn from it so we can make a better future.

Drawing from Foucault's seminal concept of Biopolitics, Achille Mbembe formulated his idea of Necropolitics. If Foucault's biopolitics is a system that governs the life of the population through biopower, Mbembe's Necropolitics is more intense and dystopian; it is often referred to as “politics of death,” in which state powers control the life and death of the population through the fear of death. It attaches life to death through austerity, immiseration, and merciless exploitation of the ecosystem. We can say that the People of Bengal were subject to this necropolitics, and it became a perfect weapon for the British colonial power to demolish and eliminate the disposable Indians to keep the power structure intact and to excel as imperialists. Inspired by Mbembe's necropolitical ideas, Christine Quinan also suggests in her contribution that a necropolitical state differentiates its population into legitimate subjects and illegitimate non-subjects. There is even targeted killing and deep-seated prejudices against Indians because of their different background. Mbembe's world is very similar to a race and caste-ridden Indian society. Mbembe defines necropolitics as “The ultimate expression of sovereignty resides, to a large degree, in the power and the capacity to dictate who may live and

who must die.” (11) Now, Giorgio Agamben's concept of the “state of exception”, intersects with necropolitics and biopolitics in its examination of power dynamics during times of crisis. In a state of exception, governments suspend normal legal frameworks, granting themselves unchecked authority that often involves decisions about life and death. This mirrors the dynamics of necropolitics, which focuses on the politics of death and the power to determine who lives and who dies. According to Agamben, “The state of exception is the sovereign decision on the threshold between violence and law” (Agamben 27). Here, he emphasises the power of the sovereign to suspend legal norms in times of crisis, thereby blurring the distinction between legitimate authority and arbitrary rule.

Through the lens of Foucault's ‘Biopolitics’, Mbembe's ‘Necropolitics’, and Agamben's ‘State of Exception’. The endeavour is an attempt to understand British policies and actions and how those were directly responsible for this particular event. Bhattacharya's novel is a living example to showcases the unsaid realities of the event. The above-mentioned lenses are essential for scrutinising the event, as these theories and ideas are well-suited for exposing the nature of a sovereign, authoritative government that exploits the basic rights of its citizens during a ‘state of exception’ or emergency. However, extensive research has been conducted to determine the actual cause of the famine, and it has been found that the cause of the famine was not one, but many.

Bhattacharya and the Famine

Bhavani Bhattacharya (1906-1988) was an Indian English writer who is famous for his socio-political realistic novels like *So Many Hungers!*, *And He Who Rides a Tiger*, *The Golden Boat*, *Music for Mohini* and *A Goddess Named Gold*, and some others. Born in Bengal Presidency in British India, he received his Bachelor's degree from Patna University, and after he went to London, where he received his PhD degree from the University of London. He was influenced by Marxist ideas and was against British imperialism. Even his doctoral thesis was also on the socio-political movements

in Bengal in the nineteenth century. From the very beginning, it was against British colonialism and imperialism. He took different jobs, returned to India, served as a diplomat, became a teacher, taught literary studies in various institutions, he also worked as a journalist. However, he turned to become a writer and started translating some of the poems of Rabindranath Tagore. And it was Tagore who asked him to write a novel in the English Language. So, he started working on the novel *Music for Mohini*, but destiny had other plans for him. The famine of Bengal had already started, and he was deeply influenced and affected by this event. It is because of this particular event that he started the novel, *So Many Hungers!* It was followed by *He Who Rides a Tiger*, a novel loosely based on the same event of famine. Many critics regard the latter as more well-structured and mature since the plot structure is an engaging one. However, the prime objective of this paper is to portray the famine through the lens of biopolitics and necropolitics, and for this purpose, the novel, *So Many Hungers!* seems more convincing and apt.

The title, *So Many Hungers!*, is layered and multi-dimensional with special attention to the use of the word ‘hungers.’ The plural form of the word Hungers with an exclamation mark at the end makes it more poignant and effective. The different pangs of hunger can be the hunger for power, for an ideal world, for freedom, for money, for sex, and for food, etc. The novel touches on many socio-political events of India at the time, like the Quit India Movement, the Indian Freedom Struggle, and most importantly, the Second World War, and the great Bengal famine. Incidentally, the novel was also published two months after the Independence of India. However, the novel is set against the backdrop of two main events: the Quit India movement and the Bengal famine. Devish Basu, one of the major characters in the novel, is better known as Devta (Meaning "God") in the village of Baruni and is portrayed as an aged man who serves as the prototype of Mahatma Gandhi in the novel. His son Samrendra Basu, on the other hand, is a barrister and owner of Cheap Rice Ltd. Samrendra Basu is opposite to his father, and he is always

looking to make a profit in times even in times of crisis. He has two sons, Rahoul and Kunal. Rahoul is an academician influenced by his grandfather and wanted to be with him in his journey to make India Free from the British. Devish Basu has left his home and dedicated his life to the villagers, especially Kajoli and her family. The plots of the novel have parallel development; on one hand, Devish Basu and Rahoul are showing the development of the Quit India Movement along with Gandhiji and Nehru, and on the other hand, Kajoli and her family show the dreadful scene of the famine. In one part, Devish Babu, along with his grandson, is helping the poor villagers and fighting against the British forces and gets arrested for their act of protest against the government. Kajoli and her family demonstrate how far a famine can impact the lives of ordinary people and families like theirs.

The Necropolitical Study

Achille Mbembe, a Cameroonian philosopher, political theorist, and post-colonial scholar, introduced the concept of “necropolitics” in his work, particularly in his book “Necropolitics.” Necropolitics refers to how political power operates through the control and manipulation of mortality and the infliction of death upon certain bodies or populations. “The ultimate expression of sovereignty resides, to a large degree, in the power and the capacity to dictate who may live and who must die.” (Mbembe 11) Though Foucault’s Biopolitics inspires his main argument, it is often said that Mbembe starts where Foucault ended his idea. Mbembe interprets the idea in a more modern sense, especially in the way in which modern states function. In the novel, *So Many Hungers!* we see how the man-made famine caused millions of deaths and exposed many people to diseases, as the following lines go. “Haven’t you ever looked at the pavements of our city as you drive by? The filthy bodies of both men and women, old and young, strewn all about? Ugly sight. (Bhattacharya, *So Many Hngers!* 154)”. The above imagery shows the necropolitical site that Mbembe is putting before us. The term Necro is a Greek word that means ‘dead person’ or ‘corpse,’ and if

we study the novel carefully, we will witness a series of deaths and dead bodies. Even in one of the famous scenes of the novel, where Kajoli and the family are coming back, Kajoli's mother notices a strange sight in which the mother of a child is burying her child alive.

The young woman, about Kajoli's age, seemed intent on herwork. She did not hear the stranger's feet or feel her presence. It was a trench she had dug, a cubit deep, and the mother watched her in amazed silence. The woman turned aside and picked up the bare-limbed baby boy, rocking him in her arms as he whimpered faintly, and coaxing, warm and tender: "No more hurt in the belly, my sweet one, my godling. You will sleep." And she laid the child in the trench, folded his reed-like arms over the bony chest and pushed the eyelids down as though to put the child to sleep, and then with hurried hands she began to pile the earth back into the grave. (Bhattacharya107)

When they inquired about the reason for the act, she answered, "Poor godling, so hurt with hunger! Look, my breasts have no milk", lifting the tatters that half covered her bosom "he has no throat to cry. If he sleeps a little! Where is sleep? He is hurt, and hurt all the time with his hunger. In his cool earth-bed he can close his eyes, sleep."(108) The reply gave a huge shock to Kajoli and her mother, they further discovered that she is the fisherman's newly-wed wife and had no option after her husband was missing. This is the necropolitical site where she had no option but to bury her dear child alive. The British people have ruled us for a pretty long time, and they had also promised a better life to their racial inferior Indian subjects, but what they had offered was famine, especially in the Bengal region. Many researchers have shown how the British could have avoided the famine, but it had to happen. Authors like Madhushree Mukherjee in her famous book, "Churchill's Secret War: The British Empire and the Ravaging of India during World War II", and another article by Zareer Masani, entitled "Churchill and the Genocide Myth" have time and again

questioned policies of the then wartime British Prime Minister Winston Churchill and investigated his true nature of dominance and sovereignty.

In another scene of the novel, we are introduced to a character named, Prokash, he is a researcher under Rahoul who worked under him. Prokash is a dedicated scholar who has no other interest than the laboratory. On one such occasion, when he was in the laboratory, he encountered Rahoul and discussed a few topics. Suddenly, Rahoul asked him whether he had gone to jail, and he replied, “So many times I have gone to Alipore Prison to see my father- four years he has been there”. (Bhattacharya 38) Now, Prokash reveals his real state and his family's condition. In the family is the only bread earner, who has to support his mother and widowed sister with children, Prokash is a revolutionary character, but because of his family, he can't do anything outwardly against the British. However, the British Government captured his father without any solid ground. On questioning why he was in prison, Prokash replied, “He loves his country” (38). Through his words, we can sense the dystopian state of India under foreign rule. he speaks in a low voice, and always looks around as if he is under some surveillance or panopticon (Foucault's Panopticon). Prokash wanted to contribute to the freedom struggle like his father, but he couldn't because a biopolitical state controls and regulates the life of the people like Prokash. In a response to Rahoul, he said, “You see, sir, I have to support my mother and a widowed sister with children. There's my research grant, and I have taken up private tuition. If I go, my dependents will starve. Otherwise...” (Bhattacharya 39)

So, it is again an instance that how the state controls the life of its citizens. The advanced form of this oppression can be the famine that caused all the havoc. However, apart from the famine, the Indian Independence and the Second World War struggle also developed and co-existed almost in parallel. That is the nature of the British rule during that particular time; we can affirm it as the ‘state of exception’. The concept of the “state of exception”

originates from political and legal theory, particularly associated with the work of political philosopher Carl Schmitt. It refers to a situation in which the normal legal and political order is suspended or overridden in the face of a crisis or emergency. Schmitt argued that the sovereign power, usually the state, has the authority to declare a state of exception, thereby temporarily suspending the rule of law to deal with an existential threat to its existence. Building upon Schmitt's work, Agamben further developed the concept of the state of exception in his influential book "State of Exception" (2003). Agamben argues that the state of exception has become the norm in modern democracies, where governments employ emergency powers and measures in times of crisis, leading to the erosion of civil liberties and the consolidation of sovereign power. In this novel, we have witnessed how state power is used to regulate the lives of the Bengali people who have suffered because of this reason

Foucault's concept of biopolitics examines how states exercise control over populations through the regulation of bodies and life processes, and it intersects with the idea of the state of exception. Now, during the famine, a kind of State of exception was created by the British government for their profit. An instance is shown in the novel where an alarming conversation takes place between Kanu and a young fisherman when they are returning from somewhere on a boat. The discussion was a fearless commentary on the age in which they are living, starting from colonial policy and the nature of their power to the emergency state in which they are living. They also commented on the world situation at that time, how big power states were devouring inferior states here one name was echoed every time, which was Japan. Kanu and his friends even called them 'aliens' as well. "Aliens," said Kanu, and made a face. "Aliens all- Engraze and German and Chinee and Japanee." "And Iranee and Turanee and Armenee," the fisherman contributed the names he knew. Aliens all. Why don't they keep to their own hearth? (47)

The urgency in their movements is due to the imminent threat posed by boat wreckers who have been seizing boats in the area, likely as part of a strategic effort to hinder potential Japanese invasions during World War II. As they row, Kanu and the fisherman discuss the importance of boats to their livelihoods and express frustration at the boat wreckers' actions. These boat wreckers, acting on behalf of the ruling authorities, have been seizing boats under the pretext of strategic necessity, compensating the owners but causing resentment and hardship among the local fishermen. They mourn the loss of boats, lifelines for fishing, travel, and survival, symbolising body and soul. Hiding one with Kanu, he faces a boat-wrecker who, despite desperate pleas, seizes it under government orders and claims of compensation, stripping them of livelihood, dignity, and sovereignty in the process. Foucault described biopolitics as, a technology of power for modern nation-states to control large groups of people: “an explosion of numerous and diverse techniques for achieving the subjugations of bodies and the control of populations” (Foucault, *History of Sexuality* 140) Now, this plot can be interpreted through the lens of necropolitics, as in how power and sovereignty can be used to dictate who lives and who dies. Necropolitics also extends the concept of biopolitics, which focuses on the management of life, to consider how certain populations are targeted for death or subjected to conditions that render their lives disposable.

So into the village of Baruni, as into five hundred others, the boat-wreckers had come, agents of the rulers, with soldiers to help them. Fifty boats they had seized, but a few were missing. Runaways! The boat-wreckers carried a typed list for each village... (Bhattacharya 46)

The action directly impacts the livelihoods of the fishermen, who rely on their boats for survival and economic sustenance. By depriving the fishermen of their boats, the ruling authorities are not only exerting control over their lives but also exposing them to conditions that threaten their existence. The loss of their boats means a loss of mobility, economic opportunities, and even access

to food, as fishing is a primary source of sustenance for these communities. Despite the fishermen's protests and appeals for mercy, the boat wreckers prioritise the interests of the state and the maintenance of authority, even at the expense of human lives and livelihoods.

Conclusion:

Winston Churchill's racial prejudice played a decisive role in the Bengal Famine of 1943, which claimed millions of lives. Viewing Indians as inferior in a social Darwinian order, he diverted food supplies to British forces and Greece while Bengal starved. This famine, a brutal product of British imperialism, exposed how colonial power exercised sovereignty over life and death, rendering populations disposable. While the West condemned Nazi atrocities, it remained silent on this catastrophe. Writers like Bhattacharya, Sukanta Bhattacharya and Manik Bandyopadhyay bore witness through their works. Bhattacharya's novel captures the intersection of biopolitics and necropolitics, portraying how famine, governance, and systemic violence stripped Bengalis of dignity, survival, and fundamental rights to life.

As we navigate the conclusion of this exploration, it becomes evident that the themes of sovereignty over life and death remain profoundly relevant in contemporary contexts. The echoes of necropolitical and biopolitical dynamics continue to reverberate in our world today, manifesting in various forms of social inequality, political oppression, and humanitarian crises. Therefore, *So Many Hungers!* not only serves as a historical account of the Bengal Famine but also as a compelling commentary on the enduring struggle for dignity, justice, and the recognition of every individual's right to life. Through its vivid portrayal of human resilience and resistance, the novel invites us to confront these pressing issues and strive toward a more equitable and compassionate future. It is important and relevant as, in our modern democratic society, governments are doing everything to regulate and control the life and death of certain populations. As we have seen in this case, the so-called British government, a

modern and civilised people, has committed one of the heinous crimes during the colonial period. It is also very evident how governments often make some decision that benefits a particular population, and on the other hand, the same decision can prove a disaster to some populations.

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